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Generation Z: Concept of Masculinity in Courtship Discourse

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Abstract

The concept of masculinity has various meanings based on Filipino thought, which is also associated with the man having his own family, the foundation of society, making it essential to strengthen relationships, especially for parents that starts during courtship. Courtship is vital in the country's culture, but it has changed due to modern technology leading to the rise of online dating. In Generation Z, it is typical to quickly start and end relationships, which has a negative impact on couples born from online dating and to their children. On the other hand, some studies also prove its positive effects on couples. In this research, using the transcendental phenomenological approach, ten participants were chosen through purposive sampling. They underwent in-depth interviews, and after thematic analysis, the results showed that courtship has different meanings based on the participants' experiences; the character of the woman being courted is most important to them; courtship is still divided into traditional and modern methods; and when rejected, men must accept and respect it. Based on the results, the researchers were able to provide conclusions and recommendations needed for further research.

Keywords: *masculinity, courtship, generation z*

Introduction

The concept of "pagkalalaki" (masculinity) is not just a translation of the English word, but a concept in Filipino thought that has different meanings depending on the context in which it is used. According to De Castro's (1995) study, he clarified the difference between "pagiging lalaki" (being male) and "pagkalalaki" (masculinity). The former has only an empirical basis tied to the possession of male genitalia, while the latter is a sociological and psychological concept that refers to the role played by a person in the family and society shaped by the society they live in without disregarding their personal views on their gender. This concept can be linked to the study of Aguilin-Dalisay et al. (1995), which showed that a person's masculinity is formed based on biological, socio-cultural, and psychological factors. From these studies, it can be seen that "pagkalalaki" has different meanings depending on the perspective used by an individual. It cannot be limited to just one definition, as this may invalidate other explanations that have a significant impact on Filipino thought and culture. Therefore, it is essential to continue studying the concept of masculinity to broaden and deepen understanding of it in various contexts.

In relation to the study of Aguilin-Dalisay et al. (1995), it was mentioned that among men from three cultural groups in the Philippines (Tagalog, Ilonggo, and Maranaw) who were interviewed, they considered a man to be "fully" male only when he has a family and a job. This is one of the roles they expect men to play to become fully masculine.

In the Philippines, the state put so much appreciation to family. According to Article XV, Section 1 of the 1987 Philippine Constitution, "the State recognizes the Filipino family as the foundation of the nation. It shall strengthen the family as a basic social institution and actively promote and protect its unity." The stability of the family has an impact on the country's economy. Furthermore, the family is essential for the well-being of children, who are the future of the economy and society (Sharma & Gupta, 2021). Indeed, the family plays a crucial role in the country's development, and it is essential to strengthen it in all aspects, especially the relationships between its members.

According to Thomas et al. (2017), family relationships play a vital role in shaping a child's personality. Reyes (2017) also emphasized that the family-centeredness of Filipinos enables cooperation and role fulfillment among family members, which helps shape members of society who aim for the common good. He added that close family relationships help achieve success and improve their social and economic status. The strength and stability of the family begin with the relationship between parents. A good relationship between parents helps them meet the needs of the whole family despite limited resources (Ribar, 2015). This relationship is further strengthened and formalized by the sacred sacrament of marriage.

Marriage is one of the most important aspects of a person's life, and a happy marriage is associated with good mental and physical health (Thomas et al., 2017). Ribar (2015) also noted that parents' marriage affects a child's upbringing. It is essential to have a strong relationship between parents, not only for their harmonious relationship but also for the future of their children.

Regarding marriage, it cannot be avoided that the topic of courtship will be discussed. Courtship is an essential process for an individual's development during adolescence (Viejo et al., 2020). Although there is no research on the direct relationship between courtship and family, it is crucial to study it because many people believe that a good relationship between lovers, who may become spouses, begins with courtship.

In the Philippines, courtship is a well-known method of building a community and relationships (Pasion et al., 2023). Its history, according to Ebreo et al. (2020), dates back to the Spanish colonization of the Philippines, with different customs practiced in various

parts of the country: “tapat” (Ilocos), “balak” (Cebuano), “paninilbihan” (Leyte), and “panghaharana.” Their study also highlighted the traditional ways of courtship among Filipino men. These include: (1) serenading or singing by a man outside a woman’s house, (2) asking permission from the parents to court the woman, (3) writing and sending love letters, (4) serving the woman’s family, such as fetching water and chopping wood, to win the woman’s and her parents’ hearts, (5) visiting the woman at home, (6) giving gifts, and (7) wooing.

However, traditional courtship is fading away due to modernization brought about by technology (Pasion et al., 2023). According to Atong et al. (2022), technology has made the courtship process easier due to faster communication methods. The use of phones or smartphones has become a way for young people to meet friends and potential partners more easily (Churk, 2020). Cabrera-Frias (2013) also emphasized, as cited in Atong et al.’s (2022) research, that online and traditional courtship provide similar experiences.

As a result, there has been a change in the way people court. In the study by Ebreo et al. (2020), it was mentioned that love letters have been replaced by sweet messages sent via cell phone; men no longer ask for permission from parents but instead directly ask the woman if she can be courted; trust is built faster now often through constant messaging or chatting; the formality of courtship has changed as men can now court women anywhere; and the process of courtship has become easier with men no longer needing to chop wood or fetch water, but instead simply spending time with the woman, buying her food, and giving gifts.

It also seems that the level of serenading has decreased, as it can now be done anywhere, not just in front of the woman’s house (Pasion et al., 2023). Additionally, due to technology, online dating apps have become popular, allowing people to meet potential partners, and if lucky, their future spouses. According to Quah and Kumagai (2015), online dating apps have made it easier to find potential partners, especially since their number increased starting in 2012.

The emergence and popularity of dating apps have changed the way people interact (Castro & Barrada, 2020). In the Philippines, a survey conducted by Rakuten Insight in August 2024 showed that the leading dating app in the country is Tinder (Balita, 2024). According to Tinder (2020), more than half of its members worldwide are Gen Z, and their numbers increased due to the pandemic. This clearly shows that the changes in courtship methods have been deeply experienced, especially by this generation.

Generation Z, or Gen Z, refers to people born between the 1990s and 2000s, known for using technology, the internet, and social media from a young age (Oxford Languages). Technology plays a significant role in shaping their identity, as Talmon’s (2019) paper showed that about 75% of Gen Z owns a smart device and uses it frequently. Most of them spend nine hours watching digital content. They often obtain information from online videos. Therefore, it’s no surprise that they also rely on technology for courtship.

In Fernandez’s (2021) research, it was found that Gen Z has a low regard for traditional courtship; they consider premarital sex normal; and they frequently use social media to meet people they might have a relationship with, which is why short-term relationships and quick breakups are typical among them. This is far from traditional courtship, which aims to get to know one’s desired partner and eventually be with them in a lifelong relationship. However, the same study also showed that Generation Z believes it is essential for each individual to find someone to love.

In some reviews, it was found that online daters often lie to impress others, which is why many women believe it’s not safe to meet people through online dating apps (Anderson et al., 2020). Participants who met their spouses through online dating experienced lower satisfaction and stability in their marriage (Sharabi & Dorrance-Hall, 2024), and this is more common among women (Bleize et al., 2024).

In the Philippines, the loss of parental control over their child’s marriage is considered a reason for its instability (Abalos, 2017). In Madla et al.’s (2019) study, it was found that there is a change in young people’s views on the concept of marriage due to experiences from their broken families. This includes fear from negative experiences, difficulty trusting others, and low self-esteem.

On the other hand, previous research by Cacioppo et al. (2013) showed that Americans who got married between 2005 and 2012 and started with online dating had a lower likelihood of leading to divorce. Additionally, Rajabi et al.’s (2016) study found that nurses who chose their spouses based on their style and standards were happier in their relationships.

These contrasting studies demonstrate the importance of studying the concept of masculinity in the context of courtship in the current era, as it is related to broader topics such as family, children, and the country as a whole. Therefore, this study aims to explore the concept of masculinity in a new context to gain a deeper understanding of it. The study is essential because the Philippines, as a state, places great value on the role of the family in society, which begins with a successful courtship. The findings will contribute to broader discussions about family, children, and societal development. As the Philippine Constitution underscores the significance of family, this study highlights the need to preserve the values of courtship in strengthening familial bonds, regardless of generational changes.

Research Questions

This paper aims to study and understand the courtship of Generation Z. The following specific objectives were served:

1. What is the definition of “courtship” to modern men?
2. What are their desired qualities in a woman?
3. What methods do they use in courting?

4. How do they cope from rejection?

Methodology

Research Design

This study is qualitative, using a transcendental phenomenological approach with a saturation of 10-15 participants. The goal is to better understand the experiences and perspectives of the participants regarding the concept of masculinity in courtship. This design was used to easily gather data from selected participants. According to Creswell (2013), the transcendental phenomenological approach is necessary because it provides an appropriate response and framework for data collection based on the participants' experiences and perspectives.

Participants

This study used purposive sampling to determine the specific participants. It had ten (10) male participants who fit the category as (1) Generation Z; (2) born between 1995-2012; and (3) have experienced courting one or more women on different occasions. According to Merriam Webster Dictionary, Generation Z refers to people born between 1995 and 2012, and this generation is skilled in using technology and responsible youth. The researchers chose Generation Z as participants because their age is estimated to be between twelve (12) and twenty-nine (29) years old, which the researchers expect to have extensive experience with the concept of masculinity in courtship.

Instrument

The researchers used a semi-structured survey questionnaire containing questions reviewed by registered psychologists in Tacloban City. The questionnaire had four main questions aimed at answering each objective of the research.

Procedure

In data collection, the participants underwent in-depth interviews. However, before the actual interview, the researchers created and sent a letter containing information about the study and an invitation to the participants to be part of it. Upon receiving confirmation, the researchers set a date and time for the interview. Before the formal interview, the researchers again explained the study's purpose and presented the ethical considerations; they also obtained the participant's consent to use audio recording devices during the interview. The participants were given the freedom to respond using any language they were comfortable with.

Data Analysis

The data collected from the participants were analyzed using thematic analysis. Thematic analysis, according to Braun and Clarke (2006) in Nowell et al.'s (2017) paper, is a method for identifying, analyzing, organizing, describing, and reporting themes from the collected data. In this way, the researchers examined the similar themes or ideas from the participants' responses to form a clear description and understanding of Generation Z's concept of masculinity in courtship.

Ethical Considerations

The research was conducted with respect for research ethics. Before starting the study, the researchers obtained permission from the participants through a formal letter. It was ensured that the participants understood their right to refuse or leave the study at any time without any punishment or negative effect. Their responses were treated as confidential and used only for the study's purpose. To maintain the privacy of their information, pseudonyms or aliases were used in analyzing and reporting the data. In all stages of the research, proper care was taken to protect their rights and dignity as participants.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data collected by the researchers, including their analysis and interpretation. To be organized, the researchers used tables with corresponding explanations.

Definition of Courtship

The first objective of this research was to determine the definition of courtship according to the participants. Their definitions of the word are as follows:

Table 1. *Meaning of Courtship*

<i>Themes</i>	<i>Definition</i>
Courtship as an Expression of Interest and Respect for Women	Courtship is showing interest or intent toward a woman or person you like. (P1) It is a process of expressing interest and seeking the chance for a romantic relationship, showing respect and dedication to the woman. (P4) Courtship is expressing emotions and interest in someone using modern methods like chatting or calling, but with respect and sincerity. (P6) Courtship is showing a woman that you are interested or have feelings for her. (P9)

Courtship as a Way of Valuing and Properly Treating Women	It is part of Filipino culture where a man shows value to a woman by giving her flowers, chocolates, and other things she likes. (P2) A form of wooing and treating the woman like a princess. (P8)
Courtship as a Process of Expressing Feelings to a Woman	Courtship is a slow process aimed at making a woman fall in love. It involves simple friendship, occasional sweet words, and demonstrating good character using technology. (P3) It is a way of expressing feelings or affection toward a woman, bringing joy, and coming from the heart. (P5) It means getting to know each other’s character. (P7) Courtship is an action where one tries to make a woman fall in love to build a deeper relationship. (P10)

The table contains data on the participants’ definitions of the word courtship. The researchers formed three themes from their responses, which include: (1) courtship as an expression of interest and respect for women; (2) courtship as a way of valuing and properly treating women; and (3) courtship as a process of expressing feelings to a woman.

Courtship as an Expression of Interest and Respect for Women. This theme has the most responses, where participants explained that courtship starts with showing interest or motivation, which will lead to the desired romantic relationship. According to the participants, “it is a process of expressing interest and seeking the chance for a romantic relationship, showing respect and dedication to the woman” (P4). According to Cruz (2014), love has many meanings, from other things that give a little joy, sometimes reaching the point of sacrificing one’s life. It can be an intense feeling that affects emotions and life status.

Courtship as a Way of Valuing and Properly Treating Women. Two participants responded, saying that courtship is giving value and showing proper treatment to the woman by giving her what she wants or needs, such as flowers, chocolates, and being treated like a princess. According to one participant, “it is part of Filipino culture where a man shows value to a woman by giving her flowers, chocolates, and other things she likes” (P2). This was supported by Santiago (2013), who defined courtship as the act or period of wooing a woman to be your partner. It is the act of making someone fall in love with you, and due to cultural differences, there are different ways of “courtship” or attracting a woman.

Courtship as a Process of Expressing Feelings to a Woman. This is the third theme, where participants explained that courtship goes through a process of gradually expressing their love to the woman. The only goal is to make the woman fall in love, leading to a deeper relationship. One of the ways participants mentioned is, “courtship is a slow process aimed at making a woman fall in love. It involves simple friendship, occasional sweet words, and demonstrating good character using technology” (P3). This was not supported by William (2013), as he stated that traditional courtship requires sufficient courage and a plan to invite a woman on a date, and technology removes this idea through simpler and faster methods through text messages, chat, or tweets.

Based on the results of the data analysis, the participants have different definitions due to their varying experiences and the women they court. This result is related to the study by Fabic et al. (2009), where they mentioned that the definition of courtship may vary, but it will still lead to the same idea of having a complete relationship between a woman and a man.

On the other hand, Michell’s (2017) study showed that courtship in the Philippines follows a series, steps, and stages. In Western courtship, it shows direct courtship or suddenness, while in the Philippines, the process is more indirect and careful. These steps include having and/or showing interest, teasing, getting to know friends, non-formal encounters, and others.

Desired Qualities in a Woman

Another objective of the research was to determine the desired qualities of a woman to be courted by a man from Generation Z. The responses formed various themes, which can be seen in the following table:

Table 2. *Desired Qualities in a Woman*

Theme	Quality	Explanation
Character	Family-Oriented	How she treats her parents and family reflects how she will treat our future family and me. (P3) She will manage a family without difficulty. (P8)
	Sense of Humor	To make the relationship enjoyable. (P2, P5)
	Independent	She can make decisions for herself without relying on others. (P5, P6)
	Not Materialistic	To avoid a toxic or suffocating relationship. (P5)
	Open-Minded	It reflects maturity. (P6)
	Empathy	
	Kind	So we’ll have similar values. (P7)
	Understanding	This is important for a long-term relationship. (P8)
	Not Arrogant	For a stable relationship. (P4)
	Loyal	More important than physical beauty. (P2)
Skills	Knows How to Cook and Work	For the stability of the relationship and mutual understanding. (P4)

Physical Qualities	Intelligent	This shows maturity and strengthens the relationship.(P6)
	Goal oriented	To take pride in her. (P3, P10)
	Beautiful	A bonus, but good character is more important. (P8)
	Well-Groomed	A clean appearance is more appealing. (P1, P4)
Religion	Height	Prefers women who are not taller than the man. (P1)
	Catholic / God-Fearing	To align in faith and ensure harmony. (P3, P9)

From the participants’ responses, four themes emerged regarding the characteristics of the woman they would court. These include (1) character, (2) skills, (3) physical qualities, and (4) religion.

Character. This theme has the most related responses from the participants. It can be said that the participants weigh the woman’s behavior more heavily than other bases when it comes to courtship. This basis includes behaviors such as being family-oriented, having a sense of humor, being independent, not materialistic, open-minded, empathetic, kind, understanding, not arrogant, and loyal. The participants look for these characteristics in a woman because, for them, these shape the woman’s good personality, which she will bring and show in their relationship and eventually in their own family in the future. They emphasized that these characteristics demonstrate maturity in relationships, so they can avoid toxic or hurtful relationships and instead have a light and enjoyable relationship. As one participant mentioned, “how she treats her parents and family reflects how she will treat our future family and me” (P3).

Clearly, the men interviewed from Generation Z place high value on the behavior of the woman they would court over her physical beauty. This aligns with the study by Nongkynrih, A. K. (2016), which found that both men and women value personalities such as reliability and emotional maturity in someone they might have a relationship with. Additionally, in the research conducted by Zafe et al. (2024) in Catanduanes, it was found that kindness and respect for the family were the leading behaviors sought after and appreciated by all generations in the woman they would court.

Skills. Second to character, another basis for men’s courtship is the woman’s skills in life. This refers to the tasks that the woman can accomplish. This basis includes skills such as cooking, working, being intelligent, and being goal-oriented. According to the participants, these skills also demonstrate the woman’s maturity. Furthermore, some participants mentioned that these skills are necessary “for the stability of the relationship and mutual understanding” (P4).

Indeed, the men from Generation Z who were interviewed look for a woman they can court who also possesses the qualities they desire in a wife, as they also seek the ability to manage a household. This agrees with the research conducted by Bernarte et al. (2016), which found that the men interviewed looked for a woman who knew how to do household chores and had good manners as a wife.

Physical Qualities. Although it ranked third, the physical appearance of the woman being courted is still important to the participants. This basis includes being beautiful, well-groomed, and height. According to the participants, they can proudly boast about the physical beauty of the woman they are courting. However, some of them also consider physical beauty as just a bonus because good behavior is still more important. As they emphasized, “a clean appearance is more appealing” (P1, P4).

Naturally, the physical appearance of the woman being courted is also a consideration for the men. This is important, according to the participants, when introducing their partner to their family or friends. It seems to be an honor for them to find a woman who knows how to take care of herself. This also aligns with the research conducted by Zhao et al. (2023), which found that men prefer the “good genes” related to the physical appearance of the woman being courted, based on the 3G of mate preferences developed by Lu, Zhu, and Chang (2015). This is what they look for in short-term or long-term relationships.

Religion. Lastly, although it ranked last and had the fewest responses, it is still important to highlight this because some participants still value religion when it comes to choosing a woman to court, despite the changing times. The participants were honest in saying that they do not enter into a relationship with a woman who has a different religion than theirs. As the participants said, “to align in faith and ensure harmony” (P3, P9).

It can be inferred from this that having a good relationship is not just based on character, skills, or physical qualities; it is also related to the beliefs and faith that they have. This aligns with the research conducted by Bernarte et al. (2016), which found that both women and men place high value on finding a partner who values cleanliness of conscience, has fear of God, and is prayerful.

Overall, these results differ from the study by Sepehri and Bagherian (2013), as their survey of young men and women, as well as their mothers, in Iran regarding the choice of a partner, found that men value physical beauty more than women, who value responsibility and feeling loved. On the other hand, in Jayatissa’s (2023) review, it was found that Generation Z claims to possess characteristics such as being religious or spiritual, honest, cheerful, responsible, loyal, respectful, confident, independent, intelligent, enterprising, and others that are similar to the characteristics sought after by the participants from the same generation in the woman they would court. This means that the characteristics of the woman they seek are only suitable for their generation.

Also, based on their reasons, it can be seen that the participants believe in the concept of courtship leading to marriage (date-to-marry), which contradicts the previous study mentioned by Fernandez (2021) regarding the typical short-term relationships in Generation Z.

Upon examination, it was found that the participants from Generation Z court women they see as potential long-term partners or future wives, which is why they look for characteristics suitable for this purpose.

Methods of Courtship

From the participants' responses, two themes emerged regarding the methods of courtship used by Gen Z men. These include (1) modern methods and (2) traditional methods.

Table 3. *Methods of Courtship*

<i>Theme</i>	<i>Method</i>	<i>Explanation</i>
Modern Methods	Using Messenger	Through chatting, we get to talk to each other, which develops feelings between us. I chose this because I lacked the courage to speak in person. (P1, P4, P5, P8) Connection matters more than overly formal or traditional methods. (P6) We use Messenger to talk and plan when to meet or visit her house. (P9)
	Giving Gifts	Because it is what the woman I am courting likes, and it is my way of showing effort. (P2, P6, P7) This has been a tradition in my family. (P4)
	Making Her Laugh	It shows respect for the woman and her family. (P5) This is how I captured her attention and made her happy. Seeing her smile makes me happy too. (P3)
	Spending Quality Time	It does not work if communication is only through Messenger. It is better to spend time together occasionally. (P8, P9)
Traditional Methods	Bowing to Elders (Pagsamano)	It's a tradition in our family, and I also do it when I visit her house. (P5, P7, P9)
	Visiting Her Home	It shows respect and dedication. (P5, P7)

Modern Methods. It can be seen in the table that the courtship methods used by Gen Z men include the use of messenger, gift-giving, making the other person laugh, and spending quality time together. According to the participants, using messenger makes communication faster and easier. Here, connection is more important than the process, so frequent online conversations become a way to maintain the relationship. In addition, gift-giving is considered a way to show effort and respect, while making the other person laugh is a strategy to gain their affection. However, there is a limit to the quality of time spent when interactions are only online, so there is still a need for personal meetings to deepen the connection.

According to the participants, "through chatting, we get to talk to each other, which develops feelings between us. I chose this because I lacked the courage to speak in person" (P1, P4, P5, P8). The use of social media, messaging apps, and other online platforms has become an essential part of modern courtship, affecting how young people interact and build relationships (Cruz, 2022). It is clear that traditional courtship methods in the Philippines have undergone significant changes due to technology. Delos Santos (2018) added that Gen Z individuals conform to tradition to show respect, but they do so alongside modern practices such as using apps and online platforms.

Gift-giving remains an essential part of modern courtship, as it shows intention, love, and appreciation for the person being courted. According to the participants, "because it is what the woman I am courting likes, and it is my way of showing effort" (P2, P6, P7). In modern times, gifts have become more personal and based on the interests of the person being courted, such as custom-made items or digital products, supported by faster access to technology and online shopping. In addition, gifts are often posted on social media, becoming part of the public display of the relationship (Liao & Chou, 2012).

Making the other person laugh is also an effective courtship method in modern times, as it shows happiness, self-confidence, and being easy to get along with. One participant mentioned, "this is how I captured her attention and made her happy. Seeing her smile makes me happy too" (P3). According to Hall (2015), humor has a positive effect on romantic attraction, as it brings joy and emotional connection. In modern courtship, social media memes, witty messages, and creative videos are commonly used to make the other person laugh and spark interest. However, experts emphasize that humor should be tailored to the personality and feelings of the person being courted to avoid offending or misunderstanding them (Martin, 2007).

It also emerged from the study that one of the most effective courtship methods in modern times is spending quality time together, especially since it provides an opportunity to deepen the connection and show appreciation for the other person. As one participant said, "it does not work if communication is only through Messenger. It is better to spend time together occasionally. (P8, P9). According to Chapman (2015), quality time is an essential way to express love and care. In modern courtship, quality time can take various forms, such as going out on simple dates, streaming favorite movies or series together, or even just talking on video calls. A crucial aspect of quality time is being present in the moment—without distractions like gadgets or other interruptions. Experts also emphasize that shared activities, such as cooking, exercising, or traveling, can strengthen emotional bonds, especially if they are centered around each other's interests (Gottman & Silver, 2012).

Traditional Methods. The table shows that Gen Z men's courtship methods still apply traditional methods, such as "mano po" (asking

for blessings) and visiting the woman's home. According to the participants, "it's a tradition in our family, and I also do it when I visit her house" (P5, P7, P9). The results are supported by Gutierrez's (2021) study, which found that although Gen Z is focused on digital courtship, some aspects of traditional practices, such as introducing oneself to the family and showing respect to elders, remain.

According to Jocano (1998), "mano po" serves as a symbol of respect and humility, deeply rooted in Filipino culture. Despite modernization, it remains important, especially during significant occasions like Christmas, baptism, and other family gatherings. Santos (2023) also found that young people continue to embrace "mano po" as a way to show respect.

Another traditional method of courtship that remains is visiting the woman's home. According to the participants, "it shows respect and dedication" (P5, P7). Visiting the woman's home is a traditional Filipino courtship practice that remains part of modern relationships, albeit with modifications due to modernization. According to Jocano (1998), this practice shows respect, seriousness, and intention to get to know not only the woman but also her family.

In contemporary times, this tradition is gradually adapting to modern living; for instance, initial communication often occurs through technology before actual visits. De Guzman (2022) noted that visiting the woman's home becomes more meaningful as it provides an opportunity for the suitor to demonstrate his intention and ability to interact with the woman's family. Furthermore, research emphasizes that although this practice is not as common as it once was, it remains a symbol of respect and appreciation for tradition.

In summary, the table shows that Gen Z men's courtship methods still employ both modern and traditional approaches. While modern methods focus on practicality and rapid communication, traditional methods continue to reflect a values-based approach, emphasizing respect, culture, and deep connections.

Men's Coping Mechanism from Rejection

The final objective of the study was to determine the coping mechanisms Gen Z men from rejection. An analysis of their responses can be found in the table below.

Table 4. *Men's Coping Mechanism from Rejection*

<i>Coping Strategy</i>	<i>Explanation</i>
Acceptance of the Woman's Decision	Just accept it; don't force her. Someone better will come along at the right time. (P2) Respect and accept the woman's decision. (P4, P5, P7, P8, P10)
Trying Again	Handle rejection gracefully and focus on self-growth. Stay chill; the right person will come. (P6) View it as motivation and don't give up right away, as women don't always like someone on the first try. But two rejections should be enough to stop. (P3) Don't give up; sometimes women test how far a man is willing to go. (P9)
Seeking Support from Friends	It's best to meet with friends; finding other activities to focus on can help you move on. (P1)

From the participants' responses, researchers identified three themes regarding men's coping mechanism from rejection. These include (1) acceptance of the woman's decision, (2) trying again, and (3) seeking support from friends. Each action was given a corresponding explanation.

Acceptance of the Woman's Decision. Seven out of ten participants stated that if the woman does rejects the man's courtship, he should respect and accept her decision. They added that the man should learn to wait for the right time and the person who will come into his life. As one participant said, "handle rejection gracefully and focus on self-growth. Stay chill; the right person will come" (P6).

This shows that the participants have a broad understanding and acceptance of the idea that in courtship, women have the freedom to decide, and whatever their decision may be, no matter how painful, must be accepted by men. This is related to the research conducted by Pronk and Denissen (2019), which discussed how modern courtship and relationship practices, often occurring online, have led to the development of a rejection mindset. This is because having numerous potential partners online can make users more pessimistic and rejecting. For women, the rejection mindset has become a reason to decrease their desire to form relationships. Furthermore, according to Wango's (2022) research, rejection is a part of life, painful, and can happen to anyone in any way. However, the painful effects of rejection on a person are often caused by their own actions following the rejection experience. Therefore, Wango provided steps to cope with rejection, starting with understanding rejection, taking care of one's emotions, talking to others about it, being positive, and using rejection as inspiration and motivation.

Trying Again. Two participants showed courage and perseverance, believing that sometimes a woman says no at first to test how far the man will go in his courtship. Therefore, the man should not easily give up. As the participants said, "don't give up; sometimes women test how far a man is willing to go" (P9). However, one of them also said that if the woman refuses twice, that's enough reason to stop.

This shows that some participants will try to do everything before completely giving up on their courtship. This follows Peykar's (2023) explanation of the "Four-Times Rule" by Alex James, which suggests that men can start and pursue courtship with the same woman up to three or four times. This demonstrates the intense desire of men to get what they want. However, most research and literature suggest that it's better for men to accept the woman's decision from the start (Shields, 2019; Martinez, 2024).

Socialize with Friends. Lastly, socializing with friends is essential because, according to the participants, their friends are the ones who best understand their feelings. Therefore, socializing with them can help alleviate the pain. As one participant said, “it’s best to meet with friends; finding other activities to focus on can help you move on” (P1). Finding other things to occupy his time can help him forget the woman. One example given by the participant is playing mobile games, which are more enjoyable when played with friends.

Having friends is truly important, even during the courtship phase. This agrees with the methods provided by Ries (2024) regarding effective ways to accept rejection. According to him, having connections with things and people that make you feel better can help.

In general, the results also agree with the methods provided by Regala, et al. (2021) on how to combat the negative implications that may result from unsuccessful courtship. These include finding new reasons to be happy; allowing emotions to flow through talking to friends or writing; and prioritizing self-worth. The participants’ responses also show their respect, one of the characteristics of this generation, according to Jayatissa’s (2023) study. Rejection in courtship can be painful, but with the right actions, men from Generation Z can overcome it.

Conclusions

Considering the data gathered from the study, the researchers came up with the following insights:

Courtship is a process of showing interest and respect to a woman. Moreover, it is also seen as a way of giving value to a woman through proper treatment and symbolic actions such as giving flowers and chocolates, which convey special attention. In general, courtship is a careful and humane process of showing love, aiming to build a deep and meaningful relationship.

Characteristics such as being family-oriented, kind, loyal, and having a sense of humor are considered important in building a strong and healthy relationship. Additionally, the woman’s skills such as being intelligent and hardworking are also considered important. While physical appearance has value, it is considered only a “bonus.” Religion is also important to some participants, but it is not the primary consideration. Overall, the woman’s character and skills are the primary considerations for the participants in choosing their partner, while physical appearance and religion are secondary.

The courtship methods of Gen Z men still use both modern and traditional approaches. While modern methods focus on practicality and rapid communication using messengers, traditional methods continue to reflect a values-based approach, emphasizing respect, culture, and deep connections.

The participants show a broad understanding of courtship, particularly in accepting the woman’s decision. It is essential to respect and accept the woman’s decision not to respond to the courtship, and the man should wait for the right time. Additionally, the man should not easily give up, especially if it is just a test from the woman. Finally, having friends is essential, as friends can help alleviate the pain and provide support during courtship, as well as find distracting activities.

From the study’s insights, the following are recommended:

For Gen Z men, pay attention to showing respect and interest in women through proper courtship. Give more importance to characteristics such as being kind, family-oriented, loyal, and having a sense of humor.

Maintain a balance between traditional and modern courtship methods to preserve culture and show respect while adapting to modern times.

Maintain respect for the woman’s decision. It is crucial for men to continue showing respect and not easily give up; instead, wait for the right time. Accepting the woman’s decision will be a sign of maturity and respect for each other.

For friends, provide support to men during their courtship. Friends play a vital role in alleviating feelings and providing distracting activities to avoid excessive sadness or negative emotions when the woman does not respond.

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